

The Relaxation Correction in the Theory of Electrophoresis of Nonconducting Solid Spherical Particles II

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The comparative analysis of the different theoretical equations for the electrophoresis of nonconducting spherical particles, as developed in an earlier publication, has been extended to some further mobility data of Mooney and Stackelberg for organic oil droplets of varying sizes in electrolyte solutions of constant concentration. The following equations in particular have been used : (i) Relaxation effect corrected equations of Overbeek and Booth; (ii) relaxation effect corrected results of computer calculations of Wiersema, Loeb, and Overbeek; (iii) surface conductivity effect corrected equations of Henry and Booth; (iv) liquid drop correction equation of Booth.

In a foregoing communication¹ a comparative evaluation has been made of the different theoretical treatments of the relaxation correction in the theory of electrophoresis of nonconducting solid spherical particles, by making use of the experimental data of Mooney^{2a} for Stanolind drops in alkali solutions. It has been mentioned^{1,3} that mobility data for particles of different sizes in electrolyte solutions of constant concentration are the most suitable for this purpose. It is the object of the present note to complete this analysis by using (i) Mooney's mobility data for droplets of (a)^{2a} Stanolind, dimethylaniline, tribromohydrin and iodobenzene in distilled water ; and Stanolind in $10^{-4}N$ HCl solution; (b)^{2b} various organic liquid droplets in KCl solutions (20° and 75°); and (ii) Stackelberg *et al*'s mobility data⁴ (25°) for droplets of paraffin oil (with 1% oleic acid) in distilled water (oil weighted with (a) $C_2H_2Cl_4$ and (b) C_2Cl_4) and in $10^{-4}N$ KCl solution ($C_2H_2Cl_4$ only)*.

CALCULATIONS, RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The details regarding the different theoretical treatments applied (including the equations), the method of obtaining the primary experimental data from the published figures**,

1. M. Sengupta and D. N. Biswas, *J. Colloid and Interface Sci.*, 1969, 29, 536; 1969, 30, 275.
- 2.a. M. Mooney, *Phys. Rev.*, 1924, 23, 396.
- b. M. Mooney, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, 35, 331.
3. P. H. Wiersema, Thesis, Utrecht, 1964.
- P. H. Wiersema, A. L. Loeb and J. Th. G. Overbeek, *J. Colloid and Interface Sci.*, 1966, 22, 78.
4. M. v. Stackelberg, H. Heindze, F. Wilke and R. Doppelfeld, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1957, 61, 781.

*In justification of the use of these data in the rather tedious calculations presented here it may be mentioned that the phenomenon of increase of electrophoretic mobility with particle size is rather widely observed, and is by no means confined to the present data alone. The legitimate conclusion therefore is that some general effects are involved, and it is of interest to see precisely how far the known electrical effects discussed can account for the said variation.

**Only those data have been ignored in the relaxation (ζ) calculations, the points for which fall widely off the smooth mobility vs. particle-size curves. Such data are few for Mooney's systems (two in the distilled water and one in the HCl solution systems for Stanolind: three for iodobenzene and two for dimethylaniline, both in distilled water); and rather more numerous for Stackelberg's systems (about a third of the experimental points in both the $C_2H_2Cl_4$ and C_2Cl_4 weighted paraffin oil systems in distilled water).

the procedures followed in the case of the different calculations, etc., have all been discussed previously¹. This allows us here to pass over directly to a straightforward presentation of the actual results*. The assumptions, as before, are that the oil droplets can be considered solid-like and non-conducting; also, that the electrolytic impurity in the systems involving distilled water (estimated from conductance measurements to be $\sim 2 \times 10^{-5}N$ in case of Mooney's first set of data^{2a}, and $\sim 1 \times 10^{-5}N$ for Stackelberg *et al's* data) can be taken to be KCl, since this is not critical. A temperature of 25° is assumed as before for Mooney's first set of data^{2a}. The values of the constants used are^{5,7,8}: $\epsilon_1 = 80.36(20^\circ)$, 78.54 (25°), 62.62(75°); $\eta_i = 10.05(20^\circ)$, 8.95(25°), 3.79(75°) mPoise; $\lambda_{k+} = 66.56(20^\circ)$, 73.52(25°), 147.5 (75°); $\lambda_{H+} = 349.82(25^\circ)$; $\lambda_{Cl-} = 69.15(20^\circ)$, 76.34(25°), 160.0(75°) ohm⁻¹cm². The particles were all negatively charged.

The results of ζ potential calculations using the analytical approximations of Overbeek⁶ and Booth⁷ ($\zeta_{Overbeek}$ and ζ_{Booth} respectively, using in each case the respective *inverted* series^{8,9}), as also by means of the 'computer calculation method' of Wiersema, Loob and Overbeek³ ($\zeta_{W.L.O.}$) are shown in figs. 1 (Stackelberg's data) and 2,3 (Mooney's data).

Fig. 1. ζ potential calculation from Stackelberg *et al's* data⁴ for paraffin oil droplets of varying sizes at 25° in distilled water (● : oil weighted with C_2Cl_4 ; ○ : oil with $C_2H_2Cl_4$), and in $10^{-4}N$ KCl (● : oil with $C_2H_2Cl_4$).

* All symbols used, and the different theoretical equations etc. referred to in this paper have already been defined earlier¹.

5. R. A. Robinson and R. H. Stokes, "Electrolyte Solutions", Butterworths, London, 1959, p. 12, 465.
6. J. Th. G. Overbeek, *Koll. Beihefte*, 1943, 54, 287. "Advances in Colloid Science," Vol. III, ed. E. J. W. Verwey and H. Mark, Interscience Publishers Inc. New, York, 1950.
7. F. Booth, *Proc. Roy. Soc. London*, 1950, A203, 514.
8. D. Stigter and K. J. Mysels, *J. Phys. Chem.* 1955, 59, 45.
9. R. J. Hunter, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1962, 66, 1367.

The *W.L.O. method* could not be applied³, because of the high ζ values involved, to iodobenzene in distilled water; also, it has not been applied, because of low ζ at high κa , to Stanolind in distilled water and $10^{-4}N$ HCl. The ion conductance value of neither the positive nor the negative ion in the KCl solutions at 25° being significantly different from $70 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$, the 'ionic mobility correction' to E' ($= 6\pi\eta_1 eU/E\epsilon_1 kT$) was deemed insignificant and hence neglected in the W.L.O. calculations at 25° , though it has been applied nevertheless in the calculations for 20° and 75° , in the manner appropriate for negatively charged particles.* The extent of agreement between the results from the two different *analytical approximations* being already more or less well known (see for example, Mooney's Stanolind and ois systems, figs. 2 and 3 respectively), the results of calculations with only one approximation (namely ζ_{Overbeek}) are shown, besides $\zeta_{\text{W.L.O.}}$, for the Stackelberg systems. In the case of Mooney's first set of system^{2a}, only the best available estimate of ζ being of interest, only $\zeta_{\text{W.L.O.}}$ (or failing, ζ_{Overbeek}) values are given for the three oils.

Fig. 2. Same as in Fig. 1 for Mooney's data^{2a} for Stanolind droplets in $10^{-4}N$ HCl and distilled water (systems 1, 2 respectively, with right ordinate), and dimethylaniline, tribromohydrin and iodobenzene droplets all in distilled water (systems 3, 4 and 5 respectively with left ordinates).

The expected relative magnitudes of ζ_{Booth} and ζ_{Overbeek} calculated from the respective inverted series (the following general equation 1) are interesting to consider. Since C_1 is always positive and C_3 negative (always in the case of Overbeek expression, and at least for

*The net corrections ($\Delta E'$) are insignificantly small ($< 1\%$ of E') in all cases, because the counterion-conductance factor (m_k+) is not greatly different from the reference value 0.184 in spite of λ_k+ being large at 75° . Here, for KCl 20° , $m_{\pm} < 0.184$, and the corrections for the two ions have the same (negative) sign; while for KCl 75° (cf. NaOH at 25° , ref. 1), $m_{\pm} > 0.184$ and $m_- < 0.184$, so the corrections are opposite in sign, though E' is still negative. (In ref. 1, $\Delta E'$ was always positive because the correction due to the slower counterion Na^+ was more significant).

1-1 electrolytes ($q_3 = 1$ and q_3^* positive) in the case of the Booth expression), therefore, in the inverted equation for ζ namely⁹

$$\zeta = \frac{U}{C_1} - \frac{C_3}{C_1} \left(\frac{U}{C_1}\right)^3 - \frac{C_4}{C_1} \left(\frac{U}{C_1}\right)^4 \quad \dots (1)$$

the consideration of relaxation correction upto the cubic term (i.e. $\zeta_{Overbeek}$) always leads to a (numerically) larger calculated value, irrespective of the sign of the particle charge, as compared to the calculation when relaxation correction is neglected (upto the linear term in eqn. 1 i.e. ζ_{Henry}). In calculations inclusive upto the quartic term in the above equation

Fig. 3. Same as in Fig. 1 for Mooney's data² for various organic oil droplets in KCl solutions (○ : $10^{-3}N$ (20°); ◐ : $10^{-4}N$ (75°); ● : $10^{-4}N$ (20°).

(i.e. ζ_{Booth}), on the other hand, C_4 (like q_4^*) is positive or negative according as $\lambda_- > \lambda_+$ or $\lambda_- < \lambda_+$; hence, were the coefficient C_3 exactly identical in the two treatments, $\zeta_{Booth} > \zeta_{Overbeek}$ (numerically) for negative particles (U negative) in the first case, and for positive particles (U positive) in the second. This would be natural, because only for counter-ions slower than the coions can a larger relaxation effect (described more adequately by the Booth equation) be expected. As it is, the actual results may sometimes be confounded because of the slight difference between the numerical values of the common coefficient C_3 in the two treatments,

The results of actual numerical calculations of $\zeta_{Overbeek}$, ζ_{Booth} and $\zeta_{W.L.O.}$ are in general as expected³, and similar to those reported earlier^{1,10}. The more important results are : (i) None of the calculated ζ values (not even $\zeta_{W.L.O.}$) remain constant* over the range of κa values studied. (a) In *low ζ systems* (≤ 75 mV : Stanolind in $10^{-4}N$ HCl, oils in $10^{-4}N(75^\circ)$ HCl), $\zeta_{W.L.O.}$, $\zeta_{Overbeek}$ and ζ_{Booth} are nearly equal at all κa ($\sim 10-200$); (b) In *intermediate ζ systems* ($\sim 75-110$ mV : oils in $10^{-4}N$ KCl(20°), Stanolind, tribromohydrin, dimethylaniline and paraffin oil (both C_2Cl_4 and $C_2H_2Cl_4$ weighted) all in distilled water), $\zeta_{W.L.O.} > \zeta_{Booth}$ and $\zeta_{Booth} > \zeta_{Overbeek}$ (difference at $\kappa a \sim 15$, about 8% of $\zeta_{W.L.O.}$ for the former and 4% of ζ_{Booth} for the latter), but the differences decrease steadily with increasing κa to about 2% and 0% respectively at $\kappa a \sim 100$; (c) In *high ζ systems* (≥ 150 mV: iodobenzene in distilled water) where the difference $\zeta_{Booth} \sim \zeta_{Overbeek}$ is known¹⁰ to be quite large even at moderately large values of κa , the calculated $\zeta_{Overbeek}$ values may thus be substantially different from the correct ζ potentials involved, because of the extent of uncertainty in the calculated $\zeta_{Overbeek}$ values.

(ii) The counterion (K^+) being slightly slower than the coion (Cl^-), and the particles being negatively charged, $\zeta_{Booth} > \zeta_{Overbeek}$ (though only very slightly)** in most of the systems.

The final mobility vs. κa curves (figs. 4 and 5) have been calculated as before¹, using in the case of the orthodox method of relaxation correction (W.L.O. or Overbeek (*direct* series) method) a suitable average value from among the calculated individual ζ values for each system, and in the case of the approximate method of relaxation correction by way of surface conductivity correction^{11,12} the values of ζ and σ_s/σ_1 as determined for each system from the limiting slope of the $1/U$ vs. $1/a$ plot. On comparison with the theoretical mobility vs. κa curves over the entire range of κa values following from the rigorous (W.L.O.) relaxation theory³, it would be seen that :

(1) The experimental points in the systems shown lie mostly on the right ascending portion ($\kappa a = 20-200$) of the complete mobility vs κa curves. For systems showing a rather sustained steep increase of mobility with particle size over this range of κa values, (iodobenzene, tribromohydrin, Stanolind all in distilled water, and oils in $10^{-4}N$ KCl(75°)), the surface conductivity correction method is seen to lead to better agreement with experimental results, while for systems showing mobility variation only over range of small κa values and little variation thereafter (dimethylaniline in distilled water) the orthodox relaxation correction method is more successful. The same is generally also true in case of other data analysed¹⁰.

10. M. Sengupta, and S. S. Jana, unpublished results.

11. F. Booth, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1948, 44, 955.

12. D. C. Henry, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1948, 44, 1021.

* The other possible assumption, namely that the surface charge density should remain constant instead, does neither alter the relaxation calculations nor is found to be vindicated any better by the actual experimental results, because the surface charge densities calculated from the ζ potentials found, by using the computational equation³ show the same lack of constancy as do the ζ potentials themselves, because over the κa range involved, the relation between the two is nearly linear.

** The small difference in the values of the coefficient C_3 in the two treatments (as also any small errors involved in evaluating the various functions graphically, etc.) do not generally appear to be able to confound this result.

(ii) For a few smallest particles ($a \sim 10^{-4}$ cm) in almost electrolyte free (distilled water, $\kappa \sim 10^5$ cm $^{-1}$) solutions (Fig. 3), the surface conductivity corrected mobility curves show a minimum at $\kappa a \sim 10$ -20. The relaxation corrected curves do not yet do so even at the lowest κa values involved, presumably because the expected minimum³ occurs at still lower κa values. The experimental data, though somewhat uncertain in this region of extremely fine particles, also do not yet show any evidence of the occurrence of a minimum.

(iii) The ζ values obtained in case of the relaxation and surface conductivity corrections for the different systems* are unfortunately not in such good agreement with one another as found earlier. Since $\zeta_{relax.av.}$ is generally obtained from the data for the

Fig. 4. Theoretically calculated electrophoretic mobilities (— $U_{W.L.O.}$, ... $U_{Overbeek}$, --- $U_{surface\ cond.}$, — $U_{liq.\ drop}$ (Booth)) compared with Mooney's data² (see Fig. 2 legend for details of systems).

- 1: $\zeta_{Ov.} = 50$ mV, $\zeta_{s.c.} = 65.2$ mV, $\sigma_s = 5.71 \times 10^{-9}$ ohm $^{-1}$, $\zeta_{liq} = 7.7$ mV, $\kappa/\kappa' = 10$;
- 2: $\zeta_{Ov.} = 80$ mV, $\zeta_{s.c.} = 121.8$ mV, $\sigma_s = 2.42 \times 10^{-9}$ ohm $^{-1}$, $\zeta_{liq} = 11.8$ mV, $\kappa/\kappa' = 10$;
- 3: $\zeta_{W.L.O.} = 80$ mV, $\zeta_{s.c.} = 100.1$ mV, $\sigma_s = 1.67 \times 10^{-9}$ ohm $^{-1}$, $\zeta_{liq} = 14$ mV, $\kappa/\kappa' = 6$;
- 4: $\zeta_{W.L.O.} = 82$ mV, $\zeta_{s.c.} = 120.3$ mV, $\sigma_s = 0.75 \times 10^{-9}$ ohm $^{-1}$;
- 5: $\zeta_{Ov.} = 155$ mV, $\zeta_{s.c.} = 194.6$ mV, $\sigma_s = 1.02 \times 10^{-9}$ ohm $^{-1}$, $\zeta_{liq.} = 30$ mV, $\kappa/\kappa' = 6$.

* The linear extrapolations, made for deriving the $\zeta_{s.c.}$ and σ_s/σ_1 values reported, do not involve the least square method; also, the 'averaging' represents more properly a suitable average choice over the calculated $\zeta_{W.L.O.}$ or $\zeta_{Ov.}$ values so as to ensure a good fit of the calculated mobility curves with experimental data.

smaller particles (κa small), whereas $\zeta_{s.c.}$ is obtained from those for the largest particles ($\kappa a > 70$ for distilled water, $\kappa a > 30$ for $10^{-4}N$ solution), therefore, even the limited agreement between the two as actually found may be considered encouraging. (Also significant is the fact that $\zeta_{s.c.}$ is always of larger magnitude than ζ_{relax}). Also, in spite of the scatter which the calculated ζ values show (due to experimental errors), it is still possible to discern however, with increasing κa , an increasing trend in ζ in most of the systems studied. This general increase in ζ (and the derived quantity 'surface charge density σ ') points most likely to the fact that the assumption that in systems of constant electrolyte concentration ζ or σ plausibly remain constant, is not fully justified.

(iv) The values of specific surface conductivity σ_s (see Figs. 4, 5) calculated from σ_s/σ_1 for the different systems by making use of the specific conductivity (σ_1) values of the different media, show a tendency to increase with (a) increase of electrolyte concentration of the solutions at constant temperature, as also (b) increase of temperature at constant concentration. Though the magnitudes of σ_s found, generally agree with those obtained from the theoretical equations for surface conductance at a plane double layer¹³, it remains to be seen how far the said variations of σ_s do so.

Finally, it is of some interest to see how far the observed variation of mobility with size in the systems under consideration may be attributed to factors other than the second order electrical effects considered; for example to the fact that the particles happen to be

Fig. 5. Same as in fig. 4 for Mooney's data^{2b} (see fig. 3 legend for details of systems).

- : $\zeta_{W.L.O.} = 48.0\text{mV}$, $\zeta_{s.c.} = 50.0\text{mV}$, $\sigma_s = 1.68 \times 10^{-9} \text{ohm}^{-1}$;
- ◐ : $\zeta_{W.L.O.} = 60.1\text{mV}$, $\zeta_{s.c.} = 76.1\text{mV}$, $\sigma_s = 1.64 \times 10^{-9} \text{ohm}^{-1}$;
- : $\zeta_{W.L.O.} = 87.4\text{mV}$, $\zeta_{s.c.} = 94.2\text{mV}$, $\sigma_s = 0.58 \times 10^{-9} \text{ohm}^{-1}$.

13. J. J. Bikerman, *Z. phys. Chem.*, 1933, A163, 378.

F. Urban, H. L. White and E. A. Strassner, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1935, 39, 311

fluid in nature. The liquid drop electrophoresis equation of Booth¹⁴ for the particular case when the charge distribution in the fluid of the drop is of the form of a diffuse double layer (thickness $1/\kappa'$) analogous to that in the outer solution, has been shown^{1,15} to be the most successful. The velocities calculated by using this equation in the case of Mooney's systems^{2a} are also shown in fig. 4.* (The viscosity value at 25° used are : $\eta_{Stanolind} = 1.194$, $\eta_{tobenzene} = 0.0156$ and $\eta_{dimethylaniline} = 0.013$ poise). The best values of the adjustable parameters $\zeta_{s.c.}$ and κ/κ' for the different systems are also shown.

CONCLUSION

As is well known¹⁶, the relaxation and the *normal* surface conductivity effects are fundamentally identical, being essentially the corrections to include the effect of polarisation of the electrical double layer near the charged particle surface. The relaxation correction is however more comprehensive and rigorous mathematically, and the fact that this method of correction gives by far a much fuller and detailed account of the electrophoresis phenomena need hardly be gainsaid. However, the complete treatment (computation) of the relaxation effect is as yet available only upto moderately large value of ζ (≤ 150 mV), while the analytical approximations thereto (which involve rather tedious calculations) are known¹⁰ to be incomplete at $\zeta \sim 100$ mV, and distinctly inaccurate for still higher values of ζ . The surface conductivity correction method, which is known to give equally correct results for low ζ , has thus a distinct advantage for application to high ζ systems also. This being so, the question becomes pertinent whether in the numerous instances, where the 'polarisation of the atmosphere' effect would profitably be taken into account, it is worthwhile to go in for a rigorous treatment by way of relaxation correction, or else a tolerably approximate surface conductivity correction treatment could profitably be used instead¹⁷.

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* In case of Mooney's other system^{2b}, the particular oil to which any electrophoretic mobility curve refers, is not mentioned. Also, Stackelberg's systems⁴ contained contaminants, which can legitimately be presumed to have affected the tiny motion within the droplets. Both these systems are thus unsuitable for analysis from the view-point of liquid drop electrophoresis equations.

14. F. Booth, *J. Chem Phys.*, 1951, 19, 1331.

15. M. Sengupta, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1968, 19, 199.

16. J. Th. G. Overbeek, in "Colloid Science," Vol. I, ed., H. R. Kruyt, Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1952.

17. C. T. O'Konski, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1960, 64, 605.